

bromine. Van Slyke method for the determination of aliphatic amines generally gives low results³. Determination of amines by titration of their picrates, though accurate, is tedious⁴. The development of a titrimetric procedure based on the quantitative reaction of 2,4-dinitrobenzenesulphenyl chloride with certain amines was, therefore, undertaken. The reaction is sufficiently rapid and accurate. An amine is warmed with an excess of 2,4-dinitrobenzenesulphenyl chloride, the unreacted sulphenyl chloride is titrated against sodium methoxide using thymol blue as indicator. The end point is stable for five minutes. The results obtained with some of the available amines are recorded in Table 1. Amines with ortho substituents and those rendered less basic due to negative substituents do not react quantitatively.

TABLE 1—TITRIMETRIC DETERMINATION OF AMINES

Amine	Wt. Range mg.	Average ^a % purity	Standard deviation
Aniline ^b	60–100	99.96	0.0381
N-Methylaniline	60–100	99.95	0.0058
<i>p</i> -Toluidine	50–75	98.17	0.1466
<i>m</i> -Toluidine	50–100	99.96	0.3007
<i>p</i> -Anisidine	60–80	99.13	0.0667
<i>p</i> -Phenetidine	50–90	99.71	0.0710
<i>p</i> -Chloroaniline	50–90	99.64	0.0738
Sulphanilic acid ^c	60–100	99.59	0.0418
Ethanol amine	40–80	99.89	0.0557

^a. Average of three readings.

^b. G. R., Sarabhai M. Chemicals.

^c. A.R., B.D.H.

Procedure:

2,4-Dinitrobenzenesulphenyl chloride (200 to 300 mg) prepared and purified according to the reported procedure⁵, is dissolved in 10 ml of ethylene chloride in a titration flask, followed by the addition of a weighed quantity of an amine (50 to 100 mg). Lithium carbonate (1 g) is added and the contents are swirled for half an hour at 40–50°. After cooling to room temperature, thymol blue (2 drops, 0.3% W/V, in methanol) is introduced and the solution is titrated against 0.1N sodium methoxide to a distinct brown colour.

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References

1. W. HUBER, in "Titrations in Non-aqueous Solvents", Academic Press, New York, 1967, p. 105.

2. C. L. WILSON and D. W. WILSON, in "Comprehensive Analytical Chemistry", Elsevier Publishing Company, Amsterdam, 1960, p. 778.
3. S. SIGGIA, in "Quantitative Organic Analysis via Functional Group", John Wiley and Sons, Inc., New York, 1963, p. 449.
4. J. KUCHARSKY and L. SAFARIK, in "Titrations in Non-aqueous Solvents", Elsevier Publishing Company, Amsterdam, 1965, p. 244.
5. M. H. HUBACHER, in "Organic Synthesis", Coll. Vol. II, Wiley, New York, 1943, p. 455.

Synthesis of Some New Indole Derivatives

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WE have earlier reported the amoebicidal and cysticidal activity of the compounds having amino acid esters linked to the carboxylic group of substituted indole 3-acetic acids via an amidic linkage¹. It is of interest to substitute an aryl group in place of alkyl chain of amino acids and explore the possibility of increase of lipid solubility. Accordingly, a series of compounds having substituted *p*-aminobenzoates and salicylates linked to the carboxyl group of indole 3-acetic and -propionic acids were synthesized and tested for amoebicidal activity.

The compounds(I) were synthesized by the following scheme

Dicyclohexylcarbodiimide (2 g, 0.01 mole) in methylene chloride (30 c.c.) was added to a solution of alkyl *p*-amino benzoate or salicylate (0.01 mole) and substituted indole 3-alkanoic acid (0.011 mole) in methylene chloride (20 ml) with cooling. After stirring for 10 hrs. at room temperature, the precipitated dicyclohexyl urea was filtered off, the solution washed successively with 20 ml. portions of *N* HCl, *N* potassium carbonate and

* This work is a part of Ph.D. dissertation of Neera Srivastava.

finally with a saturated solution of NaCl. The methylene chloride was evaporated and the residue dissolved in 30 ml of benzene and kept aside for 2 hr. More dicyclohexyl urea precipitated and was filtered off. The benzene was removed at reduced pressure and the residue was crystallized from benzene-petroleum ether.

Compounds were characterized by sharp m.p.s. analysis of 'N' and I.R. (Table 1).

TABLE 1 - N-ARYL DERIVATIVES OF INDOLE-3-ACETAMIDE AND INDOLE-3-PROPIONAMIDES(I)

Compd. No. I	X	R	R ₁	n	M.P. °C	Nitrogen %	
						Calcd.	Found
a	OH	C ₂ H ₅	CH ₃	1	102-104	7.9	8.29
b	OH	CH ₃	CH ₃	1	92	8.29	8.08
c	OH	CH ₃	H	1	90-92	8.64	8.82
d	H	C ₂ H ₅	CH ₃	1	140	8.33	8.62
e	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	1	82	8.69	8.74
f	H	C ₂ H ₅	H	1	106	8.69	9.02
g	H	C ₂ H ₅	H	2	102	8.33	8.60
h	H	CH ₃	H	1	90	9.09	9.41
i	H	CH ₃	H	2	80	8.69	8.98

Biological activity

(a) Amoebicidal activity against *Entamoeba histolytica*²

All the nine compounds were tested against axenic culture of *E. histolytica* at a concentration of 1:8000 and were found to be devoid of amoebicidal activity.

References

- NEERA SRIVASTAVA, RENU NATH, K. SHANKAR, K. P. BHARGAVA and K. KISHORE, *Die. Pharmazie. H.*, 1977, 12, 756.
- B. N. SINGH, S. R. DAS and G. P. DUTTA, *Curr. Sci.*, 1973, 42, 227.

Synthesis of Possible Amoebicides, Part III

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SYNTHESIS of some β - and γ -(2:4-dimethoxy-5-*n*-alkylphenyl)-alkylamines as possible amoebicides has been described.

Synthesis of a few α -(2:4-dimethoxy-5-*n*-alkylphenyl)-ethylamine and its β -isomers have already been described^{1,2}. β -(2-Alkyl-4:5-dimethoxyphenyl)-ethylamine was prepared by Kachru and

Pathak³ out of which *n*-hexyl substituted ethylamines were found to be very active *in vitro* comparison to emetine⁴. It was, therefore, considered worthwhile to prepare similar type of compounds and to examine their amoebicidal activity. Synthesis of some γ -(2:4-dimethoxy-5-*n*-alkylphenyl)-propylamines (Scheme 1) and β -(2:4-dimethoxy-5-*n*-alkylphenyl)-ethylamines (Scheme 2) are reported in this paper.

SCHEME-1

SCHEME-2

Experimental*

2:4-Dimethoxy-5-*n*-butylcinnamic acid (Ia): A mixture of 2:4-dimethoxy-3-*n*-butylbenzaldehyde (12g) malonic acid (7g), dry pyridine (75 ml) and piperidine (0.25 ml) was heated on a water bath in anhydrous conditions for 3 hr. It was then decomposed by pouring into a mixture of crushed ice and conc. HCl when a yellowish solid was obtained. It was dissolved in sodium carbonate solution and extracted with ether to remove any non-acidic material. The aqueous layer was refluxed with activated charcoal, filtered and the filtrate on acidification gave the desired acid. The acid was recrystallised from aqueous alcohol; m.p. 123°, yield, 9 g (63.1%) (Found: C, 68.25; H, 7.71. C₁₈H₂₀O₄ requires, C, 68.19; H, 7.57%). 2:4-Dimethoxy-5-*n*-amylcinnamic acid (Ib), m.p. 118°, yield, 63% (Found: C, 69.20; H, 8.10. C₁₉H₂₂O₄ requires C, 69.08; H, 7.91%); 2:4-Dimethoxy-5-*n*-hexylcinnamic acid (Ic), m.p. 101°, yield, 58.9% (Found: C, 70.05; H, 8.14. C₁₇H₂₈O₄ requires C, 69.85; H, 8.22%) and 2:4-Dimethoxy-5-*n*-octylcinnamic acid (Id), m.p. 90°, yield, 55.8% (Found: C, 71.09; H, 8.60. C₁₆H₂₈O₄ requires C, 71.25; H, 8.75%).

β -(2:4-Dimethoxy-5-*n*-butylphenyl)-propionic acid (IIa): Ia (11g) was dissolved in dil. NaOH and reduced with sodium amalgam (150g, 3%) in the usual manner. The alkaline liquid was decanted, refluxed with activated charcoal and filtered. The filtrate on acidification gave the desired acid which solidified on cooling. It was recrystallised from aqueous alcohol; m.p. 53°, yield, 10g (90.2%) (Found: C, 67.90; H, 8.18. C₁₈H₂₂O₄ requires C, 67.67, H, 8.27%).

β -(2:4-Dimethoxy-5-*n*-amylphenyl)-propionic acid (IIb), m.p. 67°, yield, 90.2% (Found: C, 68.78; H, 8.53. C₁₉H₂₄O₄ requires C, 68.57; H, 8.57%). **β -(2:4-Dimethoxy-5-*n*-hexylphenyl)-propionic acid (IIc),** m.p. 58°, yield, 91.7% (Found: C, 69.52; H, 8.79.

* Melting and boiling points are uncorrected. Only a typical experimental procedure for each homologous series is described.